

NONFUEL MINERAL RESOURCES OF THE PACIFIC EXCLUSIVE ECONOMIC ZONE

David Clague, James Bischoff, and, David Howell

U.S. Geological Survey

Abstract

The Pacific Exclusive Economic Zone contains a variety of hard mineral resources. Sand and gravel and their associated placer deposits of heavy minerals are the most likely to be developed in the near future, but offshore and deep water deposits of phosphorite, abyssal manganese nodules, ferromanganese crusts enriched in cobalt, and massive sulfide deposits all represent future resources. The distribution, extent, and formation of these deposits are poorly understood and will be clarified only with additional exploration, framework geologic mapping, and study of the processes by which these resources form.

Introduction

The recently proclaimed Exclusive Economic Zone gives our Nation jurisdiction over the living and non-living resources in 3.9 billion acres adjacent to the 50 States and to the territories and possessions of the United States. The importance of the EEZ becomes apparent when its size is compared to the total onshore area of the United States and its territories and possessions of 2.3 billion acres. Much of the 3.9 billion acres of the EEZ is located in the Pacific Ocean, both offshore California, Oregon, Washington, and Alaska, and surrounding the Hawaiian Islands, Wake Island, Johnson Island, Palmyra Atoll and Kingman Reef, Jarvis Island, American Samoa, Guam and the Northern Mariana Islands. Six major resource types have been identified in the EEZ: (1) sand and gravel, (2) placers, (3) phosphorites, (4) manganese nodules, (5) cobalt crusts, and (6) massive sulfides. The general distribution of known and likely occurrences of these six resource types in the Pacific EEZ are summarized in Figures 1-5. Each resource type is addressed in more detail in the following sections.

Sand and Gravel

Worldwide offshore production of sand and gravel greatly exceeds offshore production of other nonfuel minerals in both volume and value. In the United States, sand and gravel production is the largest nonfuel mineral industry in terms of volume. In 1980, nearly 1 billion tons were produced at a value of nearly \$3 billion. The

construction industry uses the majority for aggregate, and sizable volumes are used for land fill, manufacturing, and beach nourishment. Deposits on land presently provide nearly all the production in the U.S. However, as these deposits are depleted or no longer available owing to land-use restrictions and environmental concern, it is inevitable that deposits of sand and gravel on the seabed of continental margins will become economically competitive.

Several foreign nations, such as the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, and Japan already derive a sizable proportion of their sand and gravel needs from nearshore marine source areas. Offshore mining in England took place as early as 1897. The Dutch have removed offshore sand for shore-protection and land-reclamation engineering projects for centuries. Dredging for sand in the United States for beach nourishment began in a limited way in the early 1950's, but other commercial uses have been limited.

Several west-coast cities such as Los Angeles, San Diego, and San Francisco are already experiencing periodic shortages. Transportation cost is the main factor affecting sand and gravel price, and because transport by water is much cheaper than by truck, the use of marine sand and gravel is becoming increasingly appealing in metropolitan areas located on the coasts or having commercial port facilities.

A pressing demand for gravel presently is for construction of artificial islands off the north coast of Alaska in the Beaufort Sea to serve as oil and gas exploration and production platforms.

Sand and gravel resources on the U.S. continental shelves are enormous and the best known of the primary economic minerals. The U.S. Department of the Interior OCS Mining Policy Task Force in 1979 estimated Continental Shelf resources of sand and gravel off the Pacific coast of 29 billion cubic meter resources of sand off the Hawaiian coasts of 19 billion cubic meters, and "large" resources of sand and gravel off the coast of Alaska.

The need was recognized in the 1960's to explore U.S. continental margins in order to identify potential resources of sand and gravel. Equipment such as echo sounders, high-resolution

seismic-reflection profilers, side-scan sonar, grab samplers, and vibracores are most useful in determining important characteristics of the deposits. These are the location and areal extent, sediment composition and textural properties, thickness, as well as the overall three dimensional geologic framework and geologic history and processes of formation and emplacement. Several Federal agencies, as well as State geological surveys have conducted or funded marine studies to inventory sand and gravel.

On the Pacific coast of the United States, present information indicates that promising deposits of sand and gravel occur near Grays Harbor off central Washington, within shipping distance of the Portland and Seattle metropolitan areas (fig. 1). These were formed by reworking of glacial outwash gravel. Deposits from offshore California are relatively small and fine-grained, consisting of relict beach and fluvial materials, but demand is likely to be high. One of the most promising deposits, because of its proximity to the Los Angeles and San Diego markets, lies off Imperial Beach and consists of reworked gravel on the submerged former delta of the Tijuana River.

Sand is in short supply in Hawaii, but a potential white-sand supply is located 35 km from Honolulu on Penguin Bank. This supply is located in water depths of 50-60 m and is believed to be as large as 350 million cubic yards. This calcareous sand is located on drowned Pleistocene sea-level terraces.

Placer Deposits

As early as 1742, Shellrock's Voyage to California told of abundant beach deposits of black minerals discovered along the west coast of America. The earliest marine placer mining efforts (those prior to 1900) were primitive, largely to recover gold and cassiterite from beach sands in South America and Southeast Asia. The first commercial mining of marine placers was conducted on the beaches of Nome, Alaska, at the turn of the century as an experiment by miners who arrived too late to acquire claims on the gold creek nearby.

On the Pacific Continental Shelf (fig. 1), heavy-mineral sand of various composition and grade is estimated to be about $2.06 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^3$, which is about 0.77 percent of the estimated sand and gravel volume. Gold and heavy-mineral sand deposits occur rather extensively in relict beaches, buried river channels, and in reworked Pleistocene gravels. Many high-grade titanium and zircon sands have been inferred to be widespread. No definitive estimates are available for these resources in Alaskan waters, although there are some indications that heavy-mineral deposits may far exceed all of the remaining EEZ resources (fig. 2). The distribution and type of known major placer deposits off the west coast and Alaska are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1

Phosphorite

The United States is a major exporter of phosphorite, and world-wide demand is clearly increasing. Present land resources may be adequate for only another 20 years. Phosphorite resources within the EEZ appear to be enormous and will become increasingly attractive as the land resources diminish.

Phosphorite off the coast of California was first discovered by the R.V. E.B. Scripps in 1938. The deposit has been widely recovered from the tops of submarine banks and ridges in the California Continental Borderland, but it has also been dredged from rather steep slopes at depths as great as 3,000 meters and from the shelf to the north, near Monterey Bay (fig. 1). This deposit is considerably smaller than its eastern counterpart from the Blake Plateau, representing a resource of perhaps 115 million metric tons. The California Continental Borderland phosphorite

Figure 2

Figure 3

deposit is considered to be a lag deposit eroded from rocks of Middle Tertiary age. The phosphorite ranges in size from pellets to pavements, but most often occurs as irregular-shaped nodules.

Phosphorite has been recovered from several seamounts in the EEZ of the Pacific Ocean, where it is usually associated with Co-rich ferromanganese oxides. The size of these deposits is only poorly known at present.

Manganese Nodules

Manganese nodules cover much of the deep sea floor and appear to be a rich potential resource for Ni, Cu, and possibly Co. The richest fields of nodules both in terms of grade and abundance, however, occur in international waters of the eastern equatorial Pacific between the latitudes 5° and 15°N (fig. 3). Nodules occurring within the EEZ unfortunately are not as abundant, and the terrain is more varied. Their distribution, grade, and tonnage are less well known.

Manganese nodules have been reported within the EEZ of the west coast of the continental United States, Hawaii, and Pacific Island territories (figs. 1, 3, and 4). Known occurrences off the Pacific coast of the conterminous United States are too irregular in abundance, composition, or some combination of these and other factors to be eligible for immediate economic consideration. Thus, for pragmatic reasons only those regions of early economic promise are included in this brief summary. Regions near the Hawaiian Islands are the prime candidates (fig. 3). Nodules have also been observed within the 200 mile zones of Pacific Island territories.

Manganese nodules and crusts have been recognized as authigenic seafloor deposits in the seas surrounding the Hawaiian chain (fig. 3).

Here the ferromanganese accumulations grade into slabs and crusts which come under the Co-crusts classification. The University of Hawaii initiated investigations in the Kauai Channel in the mid-1970's. The deposits here are in water depths of 1,200 to 2,400 meters and stretch almost the entire length of the channel. A region 5 to 8 miles in width has been delineated. Nodules are commonly associated with brown clay and are believed to be erosional remnants of shallower crustal zones. Throughout the EEZ of the islands, similar deposits have been sampled. In some locations crust and slab dominate.

Exploration within the 200 mile zone of the Pacific Islands (figs. 4 and 5) Wake, Northern Mariana, Palmyra, Jarvis, American Samoa, Howland, and Baker have established the presence of ferromanganese nodules, crusts and slabs. Throughout these various locations, in many places water depth and compositional characteristics resemble occurrences in proximity to the Hawaiian Islands.

Cobalt-rich Ferromanganese Crust

The recent discovery of high cobalt concentrations in ferromanganese crusts on the tops of several mid-Pacific seamounts suggests that extensive resources of cobalt may lie within the EEZ of the central Pacific. This newly recognized resource has considerable scientific as well as economic interest. It should be pointed out, however, that their occurrence on irregular steep-sided seamounts (submarine volcanoes) introduces difficult engineering problems for recovery.

Industrial demand for cobalt, used largely for the manufacturing of jet engines, cutting tools, and hard-facing applications, has been steadily increasing, and the United States imports more than 90 percent from foreign sources (100 percent excluding recycled supplies), primarily from the southern Africa nations of Zambia and Zaire.

Figure 4

Co-rich manganese oxide crusts have been found coating hard substrates on the flanks of island and on the tops of seamounts in the equatorial Pacific (figs. 3 to 5). Even though crusts occur at all depths of water, the ones rich with cobalt occur at relatively shallow depths (1,000-2,500 m), as opposed to the better known abyssal manganese nodules. The crusts are known to be present on the flanks of the Hawaiian Islands, Line Islands, Wake Islands, America Samoa Islands, Howland and Baker Islands, Guam and the northern Marianas Islands, and islands of the Trust Territories of the Pacific. Co content ranges from about 0.3 percent for the deeper crusts to 2.5 percent on seamount tops shallower than 1,500 m. The Co content is more in the outer 0.5-cm-thick layer of some seamount crusts.

Co content of the crusts is highest at water depths of less than 2,000 m, and most favorable areas are where the sea floor is at least 20 m.y. old (and preferably more than 80 m.y.) and mostly free from sediment accumulation. Thus, the ages and elevations of the target sea-floor areas become important considerations in planning surveys.

In general, cobalt contents increase with decreasing depth of water and with decreasing latitude, that is with proximity to the equator. There is speculation that Co-contents also vary with longitude. These variations may be due to biological productivity within the surface waters of the ocean. As plankton die and sink to the sea-floor the organic matter is oxidized with depletes the ocean water in oxygen between the depths of about 200 and 2000 m. Seawater with little oxygen can hold more Mn and Co in solution so that crusts that form within the 200 to 2,000 m depth range accumulate more of these elements. In addition, the shell portion of the plankton dissolve between 4,000 and 5,000 m below sea level, releasing iron and copper to seawater. Crusts and nodules that form within the 4,000 to 5,000 m depth range are richer in Fe and Cu, which dilute the Co contents of these deeper forming crusts.

Important questions that need to be addressed include: (1) what is the distribution of Co-rich crusts, (2) what are the local variations, and (3) what oceanographic and topographic conditions influence crust formation and crust thickness.

The importance of this resource type was recognized in 1981, and at present its distribution is little understood. Typical crust substrates are hydrothermally altered basalt, phosphorite, and hyaloclastite containing fragments of vesicular basalt. The mean crust thickness of more than 2 cm in upper slope areas may yield accessible concentrations of about 16 kg per square meter of encrusted surface. Monetary values of Co, Ni, Cu, Pt, and Mo contents per square meter are significantly greater than values of comparable materials from known deep-water nodule sites.

Massive-sulfide Deposits

Recently, a new type of sea-floor mineral occurrence, which may prove to be of great economic value, has been discovered in several parts of the eastern Pacific Ocean. These deposits are sea-floor massive sulfides found along sea-floor spreading centers. Several sea-floor spreading centers that occur within the EEZ are Gorda Ridge and the Mariana back-arc basin.

Massive-sulfide deposits are prominent features in many land-based ophiolite complexes of the world, and have provided substantial tonnage of copper, zinc, and silver in such places as Oman, Cyprus, Turkey, Italy, Canada, the Philippines, India, and the Soviet Union. Ophiolites are fragments of ancient ocean crust emplaced along continental margins during collisions between lithospheric plates.

The suspicion that ophiolite-related massive-sulfide deposits originally formed as a result of sea-floor volcanism was confirmed by the dramatic discovery in 1979 of hydrothermal vents on the East Pacific Rise at the mouth of the Gulf of California (EPR, 21°N latitude, Fig. 1). Using the manned submersible ALVIN, investigators found active hydrothermal vents with fluid temperatures exceeding 350°C. These vents were forming massive-sulfide mounds several meters high and composed of sulfides of zinc, copper, and iron and significant quantities of silver. Similar systems and deposits were discovered in 1981 at the Galapagos Rift, the Guaymas basin within the Gulf of California, the Juan de Fuca Ridge, and on the East Pacific Rise at 13°N and 20°S.

Both the Galapagos Rise and the East Pacific Rise near 21°N are medium-rate spreading centers (total separation approximately 5 cm/yr). The

presence of active hydrothermal vents at both spreading centers of a few square kilometers in extent suggests that the phenomenon may occur over much of the length of other medium-rate and faster spreading systems. Approximately 40,000 km of spreading ridges with spreading rates greater than 5 cm/yr lie within the Pacific and Indian Ocean basins.

These discoveries immediately led U.S. Scientists to consider the Juan de Fuca and Gorda spreading centers off the coast of California, Oregon, and Washington as possible targets for similar deposits within the U.S. EEZ (fig. 1). During 1981, a USGS cruise to the Juan de Fuca Ridge recovered samples from a hydrothermal vent area just outside the EEZ boundary. The samples, which are almost identical to those discovered at the 21°N on the East Pacific Rise, are almost pure zinc sulfide (55 percent Zn) and contain 300 parts per million silver. Such a deposit, were it found on land and in sufficient tonnage, would constitute a valuable and exploitable resource for zinc and silver. Likewise, the deposit found at the Galapagos Rift seems to be a potential copper resource, with the copper content ranging between 5 and 10 percent.

During October of 1983, fresh lavas, hydrothermal nontronite, Mn-oxides and muds were recovered by dredge on the Gorda Ridge (fig. 1). The Gorda Ridge is entirely within the EEZ and recently has been opened for leasing by the Minerals Management Service.

The process of formation of these deposits is fairly well understood. The massive-sulfide mineralization along the mid-ocean ridges are hydrothermally produced, that is, the heavy metals and sulfur are leached from rocks below sea floor by deeply circulating hot seawater and are deposited when the hot seawater is discharged on the sea floor. The actual zone of active sea floor spreading is narrow, usually only 1 or 2 kilometers in width, despite the great length of ridges. Such a geometry, and the fact that the spreading-center crests are under 2,000 meters of seawater, results in convective cooling of the spreading centers by seawater. The intense discharge of the ascending fluid is confined to a few localized and narrow channels that give rise to the isolated and rapidly discharged vents observed on the sea floor.

A dramatic reaction takes place on the sea floor where the hot (300°-400°C), acidic, metal-bearing fluid discharges into cold (2°C), oxygenated, alkaline seawater at the sea floor. Mixing produces a drastic and nearly instantaneous change in the chemical and physical conditions of the fluid, and a black plume of discharging fluid is produced. The plume consists of iron, copper, and zinc sulfide minerals that have precipitated on mixing. This precipitation process gives rise to chimneys and mounds of massive sulfides.

The foregoing implies that massive-sulfide deposits are likely to occur wherever there is submarine volcanism, or wherever a subsurface

magma chamber exists. Thus, in addition to the Gorda and Juan de Fuca spreading centers currently under study, attractive targets within the EEZ for massive sulfide deposits are the active volcanic island arcs (Aleutians and Marianas) and isolated sea-floor volcanoes (many are known throughout the Pacific EEZ, including Loihi off Hawaii).

At least 30 volcanoes have been active in the Aleutian arc since 1700 (fig. 2). The segmented line of active volcanism runs a distance of 1,300 km. Farther west, along and within a graben, the presence of several seamounts suggest that active submarine volcanism is occurring today. This area has not been studied to determine the presence of hydrothermal activity. The area, however, does seem one of the more promising regions for submarine mineralization. Other promising areas along the Aleutian arc would be in submarine locations along the axes marked by the alignment of active subareal volcanoes.

The Marianas group (fig. 5) has two potential regions of active submarine volcanism where massive sulfides may be accumulating. Submarine areas along the axis of island volcanism is one region where active submarine volcanism has been reported. The other potential area is the back-arc region, the Marianas Trough. The trough is an active spreading axis and should be given high priority in the search for massive-sulfide deposits. These paired, volcanically active features extend north and south for approximately 800 km, and both are entirely within the EEZ of Guam and the northern Mariana Islands. Considerable evidence indicates that hydrothermal systems similar to those at mid-ocean ridges are active in the Mariana Trough, which is a backarc spreading center. Preliminary work has identified an axial graben where sea-floor spreading is now taking place.

Active volcanoes of the Mariana arc lie only a few tens of kilometers east of the back-arc spreading center in the Mariana Trough. Although the tectonic framework of the arc is not well known, water depths between volcanically active islands reach 3,000 m. The areas of opportunity and high potential are vast and will require large-scale surveys for adequate coverage.

Summary

This review shows that the initial discovery of most hard-mineral resources in the EEZ was made during routine scientific marine-geologic surveys aimed at understanding the framework geology and geologic processes of an offshore region. The earth-shaping processes within the EEZ boundaries are diverse, complex, and in many places still poorly understood. Nevertheless, it is essential that this history be understood if we are to adequately understand the framework and assess the resource potential of the 3.9 billion acre region.

The integration of marine geological and geophysical data is an essential element in arriving at a level of understanding necessary for

an assessment of the mineral resources of the EEZ. We must not only develop a fundamental understanding of the crustal history, but we must also understand the basic processes that control the parameters that influence resource distribution.

The United States to mitigate future dependency on other nations for raw materials must delineate the hard-mineral resources within the EEZ. These data and an understanding of the mineral forming processes will also help in the exploration of hard-mineral deposits on land.